

Chemical Investigation of *Cassia biflora* Stems

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Myristic acid, behenic acid, chrysophanol, β -sitosteryl- β -D-glucoside and a proanthocyanidin guibourtinidol-(4 α -8'')-epiafzelchin have been isolated from the stems of *Cassia biflora*.

The genus *Cassia* (Leguminosae) comprises about 580 species distributed mostly in the tropical and subtropical regions of the world¹. About 20 *Cassia* species found in India are used for the treatment of cheloid tumours, ring worm, insect bites and rheumatism². *Cassia biflora* is a less commonly available species. Though there are phytochemical reports²⁻⁴ on *C. biflora*, there is no report of investigation of its stems as yet. We report here the isolation of myristic acid, behenic acid, chrysophanol, β -sitosteryl- β -D-glucoside and a proanthocyanidin guibourtinidol-4(α -8'')-epiafzelchin from the stems of *C. biflora*.

The methanol extract of *C. biflora* stems (7 kg; obtained from Landscape Section, CCS HAU, Hisar) was concentrated under reduced pressure which was then subjected to column chromatography over silica gel. Elution of the column with benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 19, 1 : 9 and 1 : 1), ethyl acetate-benzene (1 : 1) and ethyl acetate afforded compounds 1-5 respectively.

Compound 1 : It was crystallized from benzene-petroleum ether as colourless solid (15 mg), m.p. 58°; gave brisk effervescence with sodium bicarbonate solution; ν_{\max} (nujol) 1700 (C=O), 3350 cm^{-1} (OH); ^1H nmr δ (CDCl_3) 2.32 (2H, t, J 7.0 Hz, H-2, H-2), 1.61 (2H, br s, H-3, H-3), 1.25 (20H, s, 10 \times CH_2), 0.88 (3H, t, J 7.0 Hz, Me). It was identified as myristic acid⁵. **Compound 2** : It was crystallized from benzene, (12 mg), m.p. 81°; gave brisk effervescence with sodium bicarbonate solution. It was identified as behenic acid⁶. **Compound 3** : It was crystallized from benzene as shining orange-yellow needles (9 mg), m.p. 193°; gave characteristic color reactions of hydroxyanthraquinone; ν_{\max} (nujol) 1620 (chelated C=O), 1680 (nonchelated C=O), 3300 cm^{-1} (OH); ^1H nmr δ (CDCl_3) 12.16 (1H, s, *peri*-OH), 12.03 (1H, s, *peri*-OH), 7.82 (1H, br s, H-4), 7.70-7.62 (2H, m, H-5, H-6), 7.30 (1H, dd, J 7.5, 2.5 Hz, H-7), 7.11 (1H, br s, H-2), 2.47 (3H, s, Me). It was characterized as chrysophanol⁷ and confirmed by direct comparison. **Compound 4** : It was crystallized from ethyl acetate as white crystalline compound (50 mg), m.p. 284°; gave green color in Liebermann-Burchard reaction;

showed positive response to Molisch test. It was identified as β -sitosteryl- β -D-glucoside⁸ and its identity was confirmed by direct comparison with an authentic sample. **Compound 5** : It was obtained from ethyl acetate as light brownish yellow coloured amorphous solid (40 mg), m.p. 257-60°. Immediate appearance of red color with a mixture of 5% vanillin in ethanol (4 part) and concentrated HCl (1 part) and its hydrolysis with ethanolic-HCl was indicative of a proanthocyanidin : ν_{\max} (nujol) 3350 cm^{-1} (OH); the acetate ($\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{py}$), m.p. 128°, ^1H nmr δ (CDCl_3) 7.20 (4H, d, J 8.0 Hz, B-ring H-H-2', H-6', H-2''', H-6'''), 7.10 (4H, d, J 8.0 Hz, B-ring H-H-3', H-5', H-3''', H-5'''), 6.75-6.35 (4H, m, A-ring H-H-5, H-6, H-8, H-6''), 4.65-4.10 (5H, m, C-ring H-H-2, H-3, H-4, H-2'', H-3''), 2.75 (2H, br s, benzylic CH_2), 2.28 (15H, br s, 5 \times phenolic OAc), 1.81 (6H, br s, 2 \times aliphatic OAc); the pentamethyl ether ($\text{Me}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3$), m.p. 151°; diacetate of pentamethyl ether ($\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{py}$), m.p. 126°. It was characterized as guibourtinidol-(4 α -8'')-epiafzelchin reported earlier from *C. fistula* sapwood⁹.

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References

1. H. M. LAWRENCE, "Taxonomy of Vascular Plants", Macmillan, New York, 1951, p. 547.
2. N. JAIN and R. N. YADAVA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1994, **71**, 209.
3. M. AHMED, N. JAIN, M. KAMIL, and M. ILYAS, *Fitoterapia*, 1991, **62**, 347.
4. HEMLATA, Ph.D. Thesis submitted to CCS HAU, Hisar, 1992.
5. S. SASAKI, "Handbook of Proton-NMR Spectra and Data", Academic, Tokyo, 1985, Vol. 5, p. 83.
6. R. K. STRONG, "Kingzett's Chemical Encyclopaedia", 8th. ed., BTC Ltd., London, 1952, p. 16.
7. S. B. KALIDHAR and P. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **62**, 411.
8. S. B. KALIDHAR, M. R. PARTHASARTHY, and P. SHARMA, *Phytochemistry*, 1982, **21**, 796.
9. A. D. PATIL and V. H. DESHPANDE, *Indian J Chem., Sect. B*, 1982, **21**, 626.